

Schiff Base Complexes of Copper(II) and Zinc(II)

V. V. RAMANUJAM* and B. SIVASANKAR

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Madras, A. C. College of Technology Campus, Madras-600 025

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Copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of Schiff bases obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehyde and pyruvic acid with DL-2-aminobutyric acid, 3-aminobutyric acid, 4-aminobutyric acid, L-methionine, L-histidine, DL-asparagine and L-glutamine have been synthesized and characterized. A seven-membered ring is stabilized by its fusion with another ring in Schiff base complexes derived from 4-aminobutyric acid. All the Schiff bases coordinate through the ONO donor set derived from the carboxyl, imino and the phenoxy groups in the case of Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and two carboxyls and the imino groups in the case of Schiff bases derived from pyruvic acid.

SCHIFF base complexes of copper(II) derived from bidentate α -amino acids have been widely investigated¹⁻⁸. However, the Schiff base complexes derived from β - and γ -amino acids have not been investigated in detail. The present study involves the synthesis and characterization of the complexes of copper(II) and zinc(II) with Schiff bases obtained from the condensation of salicylaldehyde/pyruvic acid with DL-2-aminobutyric acid, 3-aminobutyric acid, 4-aminobutyric acid and the tridentate amino acids, L-methionine, L-histidine, DL-asparagine and L-glutamine.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by reacting the preformed Schiff base with the metal acetate. The appropriate amino acid (0.01 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of water and an aqueous ethanolic solution of salicylaldehyde was added. The mixture was heated over a water bath to about 50° to which the solid metal acetate was added in small amounts with constant stirring. The solid product was filtered, washed with water, ethanol and finally with ether and dried over fused calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator. Copper(II) complexes were also prepared by reacting *bis*-(salicylaldehyde) copper(II) complex with appropriate amino acid in aqueous ethanolic medium. Schiff base complexes of copper(II) obtained from the condensation of pyruvic acid and amino acids were prepared in a similar manner. The complexes were characterized by elemental analyses, vibrational and electronic spectra and magnetic data.

Results and Discussion

Schiff base complexes of copper(II) derived from bidentate amino acids: The copper(II) complexes are green in colour and are soluble in water and other coordinating solvents but insoluble in common organic solvents. N-pyruvideneamino acid complexes are blue in colour.

The analytical data on the complexes agree with the formula $\text{CuSB}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The infrared spectra of the complexes show a broad band centred around 3300 cm^{-1} indicating a coordinated water molecule. Thermogravimetric analysis supports the presence of coordinated water. The strong band observed at 1650 cm^{-1} is due to the imino group. The band at 1600 cm^{-1} has been assigned to the overlapping absorption frequencies of the asymmetric stretch of the carboxyl and the phenyl ring. Bands at 900 and 768 cm^{-1} may be attributed to rocking and wagging modes of the coordinated water.

Conductance measurements in methanol indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytes. The coordination of the monoanionic carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups to the (+2) metal would yield neutral complexes. The magnetic moments of the complexes measured at room temperature are in the range 1.8 to 1.9 B.M. suggesting the presence of one unpaired electron per metal atom.

The electronic absorption spectra of the complexes in methanol show a broad band centred around 660 nm (15150 cm^{-1}). In pyridine the λ_{max} is shifted to lower wavelengths by about 10 nm and the absorptivity also increases indicating a change in the chromophoric group from O_2N in the aquo complex to O_2N_2 by the replacement of water by the stronger field ligand pyridine.

Structure: It is evident that the ligands, N-salicylidene- and N-pyruvidene-amino acids function as tridentate ligands with ONO donor sets. The three functional groups along with one molecule of solvent (water) occupy the planar positions around copper(II). It may be noted that the seven-membered ring is stabilized in N-salicylidene-4-aminobutyrate and N-pyruvidene-4-aminobutyrate by the presence of an additional chelate ring fused to the former. In view of the presence of a coordinated water molecule in the present set of complexes and the observed normal magnetic moments for copper(II), the most probable structure is the one similar to N-salicylidene-glycinataquocopper(II)

hemihydrate wherein the carboxyl oxygen of a second molecule is coordinated to the metal of the first molecule leading to a squarepyramidal arrangement⁹.

Schiff base complexes of copper(II) derived from tridentate amino acids: The potentially tridentate acids L-serine, L-methionine and L-histidine yielded Schiff base complexes of copper(II) corresponding to the formula $\text{CuSB.H}_2\text{O}$. The presence of coordinated water has been inferred from infrared studies. The infrared spectra of these complexes also indicate that the carboxyl and the imino groups are coordinated. The imidazole group of the histidine moiety is probably not involved since the absorption bands due to imidazole ring stretch ($1490\text{-}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the in-plane vibration mode of the imidazole ring ($950\text{-}960\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are absent. The same observation has been made in the spectra of the binary histidinatocopper(II) complexes wherein it has been concluded that histidine is only bidentate¹⁰. The presence of coordinated water in the complex N-salicylidene-L-serinato-copper(II) indicates the complete occupation of the four planar sites. Further coordination of the hydroxyl group in the planar position can be ruled out from geometric consideration.

Schiff base complexes of zinc(II) derived from bidentate and tridentate amino acids: The complexes varying from colourless to pale yellow are found to correspond to the formula $\text{ZnSB.H}_2\text{O}$. They are insoluble in water, ethanol and other organic solvents and sparingly soluble in dimethylsulphoxide. The infrared spectra of these complexes show a broad band centred around 3300 cm^{-1}

attributable to the $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ stretch of the coordinated water molecule. The absorption bands due to the imino group and the asymmetric and symmetric stretches of the carboxyl group have been observed at 1630 , 1590 and 1400 cm^{-1} respectively. Conductance measurements in DMSO indicate the complex species to be non-electrolytes.

It is evident from the above data that the ligands are tridentate involving the carboxyl, hydroxyl and the imino groups. The fourth coordination site is occupied by a water molecule. The thioether in methionine, imidazole in histidine and the amide groups in asparagine and glutamine moieties of the corresponding Schiff bases are not involved in coordination. A tetrahedral arrangement of the donor atoms around zinc(II) is the most probable configuration.

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